

TEACHING SPEAKING

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Abstract:

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About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

One of the largest growing industries nowadays is education all over the world. There is a significant demand for teaching and learning the languages in the field of education. Now we lighten the role and importance of speaking in the field of education. Most of the adult learners have been showing higher results in learning speaking. First and foremost, here their personalities and memories play a dominant role in determining how quickly and how correctly they will accomplish this goal. Those who are not afraid of making mistakes will generally be more talkative, but it may be risky it means as a result gradually their making mistakes becomes habit. Students who is timid and faltering may spend too long time to speak confidently, but when they do, their English often contains fewer errors and they will be proud of their English ability. It's a matter of quantity viceversa quality, and neither approach is wrong. However, if the aim of speaking is communication and that does not require perfect English, then it makes sense to encourage quantity in your classroom. Teachers' task is breaking the silence and getting students communicating with whatever English they can use, correct or not, and selectively address errors that block communication.

Speaking lessons often tie in pronunciation and grammar, which are necessary for effective oral communication. Or a grammar or reading lesson may incorporate a speaking activity. Either way, your students will need some preparation before the speaking task. This includes introducing the topic and providing a model of the speech they are to produce. A model may not apply to discussion-type activities, in which case students will need clear and specific instructions about the task to be accomplished. Then the students will practice with the actual speaking activities. These activities may include imitating (repeating), answering verbal cues, interactive

conversation, or an oral presentation. Most speaking activities inherently practice listening skills as well, such as when one student is given a simple drawing and sits behind another student, facing away. The first must give instructions to the second to reproduce the drawing. The second student asks questions to clarify unclear instructions, and neither can look at each other's page during the activity. Information gaps are also commonly used for speaking practice, as are surveys, discussions, and role-plays. How can we improve our speaking? There are some practical suggestions to improve our speaking:

The first method is while preparing for a spoken task, teacher should make students to be aware of any relevant first language strategies that might help them to perform the task successfully. For example, 'rephrasing' if someone does not understand what they mean.

Formal and informal language. In this method teacher gives students one or more short dialogues where one speaker is either too formal or informal. Students first identify the inappropriate language, then they try to change it.

Different spoken text types. In this method teacher draw up a list of spoken text types relevant to the level of his class. Then gives appropriate explanation for each text type.

Interactive listening. In the following method teacher try to develop interactive listening exercises. According to the course books, face-to-face listening is the most common and the least practiced one among others. The most suitable option is "Live listening". It means the teacher speaks to the students.

The next method is *transactional and interactional language*. Teacher's task here raising students' awareness by using a dialogue that contains both. If we take interactional, it could be two friends chatting to each other; and in terms of transactional, ordering a meal.

Preparation and rehearsal. In this method teacher gives some preparation and rehearsal time before speaking. In order to be effective, students will need guidance on how to use it.

The last method is using real-life tasks. In this type of method most times teacher tries to give a real-life situations in order to be easy.

In conclusion, in our developing world *communication* is one of the most effective way in every realm of the business. The key of the communication is considered speaking. As we know, hitherto English teachers try to find effective ways and techniques to increase students speaking skills. As a result they somehow did it. We as a teacher or as a parents should create the appropriate atmosphere to our students or children either in class or even outside the classroom. In this case we can expect them higher results.

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